

STRAIN RATE EFFECT ON INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED pCBT AND EPOXY COMPOSITES.

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SUMMARY

The interlaminar shear strengths of carbon fibre reinforced pCBT and epoxy matrix composites moulded by VA-RTM have been characterised at quasi-static and low energy impact tests. pCBT composites show higher damaged volume but lower interlaminar shear strength, which could be a consequence of its lower tensile strength and higher void content. Interlaminar shear strength has found to be strain rate dependent for both composites.

Keywords: pCBT; Carbon fibre; VA-RTM; Impact; ILSS.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites are finding increasing use in a wide range of engineering applications. These lightweight materials, in comparison steel or aluminium, offer superior strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios, increase the impact energy absorption per unit of weight, noise and vibrations are reduced and exhibit an excellent resistance to fatigue [1,2]. However, composites have poor resistance to damage due to out-of-plane impact, and consequently this could preclude their use in some structures [3]. So, it is imperative to understand how these materials behave under impact.

Resin transfer moulding (RTM) of thermoset polymers is a well-established processing method for niche applications. RTM process requires relatively low investments and manufacturing costs, and they are obtained components with good surface finish in both faces and accurate thickness control. The thermoplastic matrix composites present better toughness than the thermoset ones. The high melt viscosity of thermoplastics is the main issue when textile composites are moulded. The thermoplastic matrix composites must fulfil the following conditions for liquid impregnation: 1) viscosity during impregnation ($\eta < 1 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$); 2) after impregnation, the matrix should be solidified in a sufficiently short time; and the reaction should proceed without any by-products [4]. Recent developments in thermoplastic RTM are promising [5-10]. Low scrap/good recyclability, better toughness/damage tolerance, unlimited shelf-life, possibility to post forming and welding, and rapid fabrication cycle are some of the thermoplastic matrices attractive features. The most usual polymer systems for thermoplastic RTM are the anionic ring-opening polymerisation of polyamides [5] and the entropically driven ring-opening polymerisation of cyclic oligoesters [9]. The main research areas that have

received special attentions are polymerisation mechanisms [9], microstructural characterisation [9] and static properties [7,9], and no research was devoted to the impact and fracture behaviour of textile fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composites manufactured by in situ polymerisation. So, the application of these thermoplastic systems is partially limited by a lack of their impact performance knowledge.

The interlaminar shear strength is one of the most important parameters in determining the ability of a composite material to resist delamination damage. An accurate determination of its value, therefore, is important. This is particularly true at high strain rates since delamination damage frequently occurs as the result of transverse impact loading [11]. This is because conventional manufacturing techniques do not produce reinforcing fibers oriented in the thickness direction to sustain transverse load [12]. Delamination growth is the fundamental issue in the evaluation of laminated composite systems for durability and damage tolerance [13]. Three-point bending test, also known as short beam shear test, is often used to measure the apparent interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of composites laminates. Even if the composites are developed for impact applications, usually the research studies have been focused on quasi-static ILSS characterization. As polymers are strain rate dependent, characterization should be carried out in the same service strain rate range [14].

This paper focuses on the low-velocity impact properties of carbon fibre reinforced cyclic (butylene terephthalate) oligomers (CF-pCBT), which after polymerisation form the engineering thermoplastic poly(butylene terephthalate), and the results are compared with an epoxy system (CF-epoxy). The main objective of the present paper is to characterise the ILSS at static and impact strain rates of this new carbon fibre reinforced pCBT composite, and to compare these values with those of an epoxy matrix composite. Mechanical tests have been completed with density, fibre content and voids content characterisation.

MATERIALS AND COMPOSITE PROCESSING

The prepolymer used in this study was the cyclic butylene terephthalate oligomer (CBT160[®]) supplied by Cyclics Corporation. This CBT contains the polymerisation catalyst and was termed as one-component CBT. The CBT oligomers are precursors for the semi-crystalline engineering thermoplastic polymer poly(butylene terephthalate) (pCBT). The number of butyl groups in the oligomer mixture varies from two to seven, resulting in a melting range from 130–160 °C. The melted oligomer (230 °C) was vacuum infused into the closed mould (heated to 230 °C), cooled to 190 °C, then it was kept for 20 minutes and finally it was cooled out of oven for 30 minutes before the composite is demoulded. Flat plates 250 x 250 x 3.5 mm³ of CF-pCBT were successfully produced.

Carbon fibre reinforced epoxy laminates (CF-epoxy) were manufactured via vacuum assisted RTM. The thermosetting system used in this study was an epoxy EPOLAM 5015 and EPOLAM 5014 hardener (supplied by Axson). The resin/hardener mix ratio was 100:34 parts by weight. In order to remove air bubbles created at the initial resin-hardener mixing stage, the mixture was left for 10–15 min under vacuum. The resin was then injected under low pressure into the mould and it was kept 24 hours at 23 °C. Finally, the laminate was heated for 16 hours at 80 °C.

The reinforcement used for both, pCBT and epoxy composite, was high strength carbon fibre fabric with balanced plain weave architecture and has a surface weight of 200 g/m²

(supplied by Hexcel, ref. 43199). Ten layers of carbon fibre reinforcement were used for each laminate panel.

EXPERIMENTAL

The density of both composites was determined according to ASTM D792-91. Carbon fibre volume fraction was measured by matrix digestion according to ASTM D3171-06 and void content according to ASTM D2734.

Scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL-JSM 5600LV) micrographs of the polished sections taken normal to the thickness were analysed to determine the 2D geometric arrangement of the fibres within the composites. Direct observation of the polished surface was carried out under low vacuum conditions.

Universal testing machine Instron 3369 for quasi-static tests and falling weight equipment Fractovis Plus for impact tests were used. The studied testing speeds were 1 mm/min, 0.98 and 1.98 m/s. Three-point bending test, also known as short beam shear test, was used to measure the apparent interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of composites laminates. According to ASTM D2344 the span was 14 mm in order to maintain the span/thickness ratio recommended for carbon fibre composites. Impact tests were carried out with a 1.984 kg striker with a 5 kN load cell. ILSS parameter has been computed from the maximum load observed during the test, F_{max} , according to the following equation 1:

$$ILSS = 0.75 \frac{F_{max}}{b.h} \quad (1)$$

where b and h are the rectangular specimens width (7 mm) and thickness (3.5 mm), respectively. The average values were derived from five test for each composite.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Density, fibre and void contents.

CF-pCBT has a slightly higher density (1.45 g/cm³ versus 1.36 g/cm³) and fibre content (34.0 and 28.8 % respectively). SEM micrographs of polished transversal cross-sections of both types of composites showed that fibres are packed into their respective warp and it seems that the inter-fibre distance in the rovings remains fairly uniform.

Void content in CF-pCBT is slightly higher (1.4 %) than the 1 % maximum microvoid content generally accepted for structural applications [15], whereas for CF-epoxy is much lower (0.2 %). The microvoids found in CF-pCBT seem to be formed in the fibre bundles. The CBT's melt viscosity is an order of magnitude lower than that of epoxy thermoset resins. The formation of microvoids is probably due to the fact that the water-like viscosity will induce significant capillary forces during impregnation of the fibre pre-form [10].

Quasi-static ILSS tests.

Representative curves for both materials are shown in figure 1. The load-displacement curves show that for both composites, the load increases linearly at the early stage of the test, and deviates from this linearity before reaching the maximum peak, which is probably associated to some plastic deformation. The maximum load point is related to the onset of failure, and this load value is used in the present work for calculating the ILSS [13]. The post peak behaviour is however different, whereas for CF-pCBT the

fracture is not catastrophic but the crack propagation requires a certain amount of energy, CF-epoxy composite shows a sudden drop with practically no energy consumed for the crack propagation process.

Figure 1. Load-displacement curves at 1 mm/min of CF-epoxy and CF-pCBT composites.

The micrographs of polished transversal cross-section of short beam shear test in figure 2 show that CF-pCBT composite failure mode is mainly by shear, even if some translaminal damage is observed, whereas CF-epoxy composite presents large translaminal breaking and hardly delamination.

Figure 2. Micrographs of tested specimens of short beam shear test: (left) CF-pCBT and (right) CF-epoxy composite

Impact ILSS tests.

In figure 3 load-displacement curves at 0.98 and 1.98 m/s of CF-epoxy and CF-pCBT are presented. For CF-epoxy the load-displacement curve is different, since in quasi-static tests the maximum load is not reached linearly, and in impact there is a straight path until the fracture point. The sudden load drop after the maximum load point is typical of the brittle fracture mode. Increasing strain rate increases the maximum load value, but has not effect in the fracture mode.

As CF-epoxy also CF-pCBT composite keeps the linearity during the impact tests until the fracture point is reached. CF-pCBT's maximum load slightly increase with the strain

rate. In both cases, quasi-static and impact, the crack propagation is progressive not catastrophic, but impact curves shows multiples peaks probably due to dynamics effects and discontinuous nature of the damage mechanism.

Figure 3. Load-displacement curves at 0.98 and 1.98 m/s of CF-epoxy and CF-pCBT composites.

CF-pCBT composite presents multiple delamination zones connected by translaminal breakage, while CF-epoxy composite shows a translaminal crack from the top to the bottom of the specimen which produces delamination, figure 4.

Figure 4. Micrographs of tested specimens of short beam shear test: (left) CF-pCBT and (right) CF-epoxy composite.

For all CF-pCBT quasi-static and impact tests mid-plane interlaminar failure, and not tensile or compressive failure of the outer layers, has been clearly observed. Consequently, the reported maximum load values could be related to the ILSS. However, for CF-epoxy specimens failed by other type of damage than pure interlaminar shear, and ILSS are not reliable. The ILSS values obtained from the short beam shear test have been summarised in figure 5. The ILSS of CF-pCBT are 27.5 ± 1.9 , 29.7 ± 1.9 and 32.3 ± 1.6 MPa at 1 mm/s, 0.98 and 1.98 m/s respectively. The quasi-static value is within the values reported by Ishak et al [7]. The ILSS values of CF-pCBT are significantly lower than the CF-epoxy's values, 51 ± 1.6 , 62.3 ± 2.8 and 66.7 ± 4.2 MPa at 1 mm/s, 0.98 and 1.98 m/s respectively. This higher ILSS value of

CF-epoxy composite justifies its lower impact energy absorption capability, as has been found in our previous research work [16], since as the ILSS increases the delamination damage is hindered, and the composite laminates tend to fracture in a more brittle way under impact conditions [17]. When the interlaminar shear strength is lower the volume of damaged material is higher and the frond is forced to sustain a relatively low crack density in order to conform to the deformation. Instead if the ILSS is high then a reduced split occurs and a greater local crack density is required to facilitate the bending of the frond [18]. Finally, the ILSS values of both composites are strain rate dependent, which is justified by the viscoelastic nature of the polymeric matrices.

Figure 5. The ILSS values obtained from the short beam shear test at different strain rates for CF-pCBT and CF-epoxy composites.

The ILSS of composites depends mainly on two factors [19]; resin strength and composite void content. It was found an essentially increasing linear relationship between the tensile strength of the void free resin matrix and the ILSS. The effect of voids depends on their size. The larger voids acted as crack initiation sites under a shear stress, whereas the increase in stress due to the reduction in net cross-section was the main factor in shear failure of composites with smaller distributed voids. Tensile strength and void content seem to be also at the origin of the differences between CF-pCBT and CF-epoxy composites, since pCBT matrix has a lower tensile strength (54 MPa [9]) than epoxy matrix (80 MPa), and has also a higher void content.

It is clear that there is a strong correlation between the through-thickness properties of a laminate, as reflected by the interlaminar shear strength, and the energy absorbed during crushing in carbon fibre composites, as was found in previous studies on glass fibre systems [18].

CONCLUSIONS

The interlaminar shear strengths (ILSS) of carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic (pCBT) and thermoset (epoxy) matrix composites have been characterised at quasi-static and low energy impact tests. All pCBT matrix composite specimens have failed by interlaminar shear, whereas epoxy specimens have broken in a mixed mode. The volume damaged during tests is higher in pCBT composites than in epoxy ones. However pCBT matrix composite has shown lower ILSS values, which is probably due

to its lower tensile strength and higher void content. Finally, ILSS has found to be strain rate dependent for both kinds of composites.

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